
PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract.

this article presents the analysis of problems aimed at improving and developing the communicative competence of students, in which the peculiarities of this problem are highlighted in a systematic and comprehensive manner.

Key words.

Ability, knowledge, education, motivation, competence, development, professional knowledge, strategy, theoretical material, success, skill, responsibility, flexibility, decision-making, command, systematic thinking, result-oriented 'direction and creativity

Introduction

The problem of communicative competence of students is an urgent problem in the field of pedagogy today, and it is necessary to pay special attention to the issues of comprehensive research of this problem. The reason is very important for students to step into independent life. Therefore, it is necessary to reveal the peculiarities of the development of communicative competence through scientific research.

Material And Methods

The systematic-structural approach based on objectivity, universality, concreteness, logical, and historical dialectical principles was used in the research. This makes it possible to see the concepts of manipulation and information as a whole system of human society.

Results And Discussion

Today, problems of developing communicative competences in the field of pedagogy are gaining importance. Therefore, a lot of attention is being paid to this problem. A number of scientists are conducting their research work on these problems in all aspects and from various aspects. Of them, D. McClelland's views are important. According to him, traditional aptitude and knowledge tests and educational information are not the most important things in the activities of these students. He claims that they will not be the basis of success in work and life. D.

McClelland says that it is very important to develop "competencies" in the characteristics, motivation and behavior of a person, which determine the main qualities of a person as follows, that is, they determine his effective behavior at work. Everyone knows the situation in front of the student, but he can't do new tasks. He says that this is exactly what happens when a person does not have management models (competencies) of behavior, despite having professional knowledge and skills.

Competence is related to the integrity of the interaction of the following qualities of students:

- Opportunities
- Personal characteristics
- Knowledge and skills
- Motivation

Each person is an individual, but there is a certain similarity between people that it is not easy for each of us to realize the need to change the habitual behavior - our "self-image" is mixed with habitual ideas. supported and strengthened.

We must emphasize that motivation is the "motor of competence" without which we cannot go anywhere. Motivation is the easiest way to acquire and master new knowledge and skills that have not been developed in practice[1, 24 c]. Personal characteristics and abilities are also developed, but to a lesser extent.

It is a very difficult task to develop competence from the minimum level to the required level, and even more so to bring it to automaticity. There are several promotion strategies, each with their own advantages and limitations:

Capacity development strategies include:

First, the development of weaknesses. Improving the least developed competences as given characteristics reduces the probability of raising them to the level necessary for effective performance of professional tasks. Restrictions are not applied to competences that are difficult to develop, where such a component as "Motivation" plays a dominant role.

Secondly, in compensating for weaknesses by active use of strengths, the following characteristics are shown, and the highly developed competencies are used to compensate for the lack of development of other competencies. Limitations It is argued that the tendency to adhere to the usual behavior limits the ability to adapt to changing conditions.

Thirdly, a comprehensive approach to the development of competencies, which features a combination of efforts to "pull" weaknesses and cover them with

the most developed competencies, allows to achieve the best results by balancing the improvement of all competencies. Thus, a comprehensive strategy is the most effective, because it allows not only to rely on one's own strengths, but also to work on the least developed competencies, to achieve balance and harmony in development, as well as the effectiveness of behavior.

The issue of ways of developing students' abilities is very important, and it is inextricably linked with the development of competencies. Abilities can be developed in several ways. In order to improve competences, it is necessary to use three main categories of development methods, each of which includes a specific method of mastering successful behavior patterns, is distinguished by its advantages and some limitations. Among them we can mention the following:

First, Saying (educational theory) - identifying successful behavior models in the process of independent study of theoretical material (business literature, video courses, searching for materials on the Internet, etc.), as well as in the process of participating in thematic training. educational programs (trainings, seminars, courses, second higher education, other specializations and other educational programs).

Second, Demonstration (learning from the experience of others) - identifying successful behavior patterns by observing people in work situations. High level development of these competencies, discussion of ways and methods that allow to achieve high results with them; as well as improving competencies by engaging a coach, mentor, and receiving feedback from experienced people.

Third, Empiricism (practical application) - acquisition of successful behavior models by regular application of theoretical knowledge in real activities, both in the performance of tasks that are part of the students' direct obligations, and in the performance of additional special assignments and projects. . Not related to the main tasks or professional activities.

First of all, competencies differ in their content and what they have: knowledge, skills, individual inclinations. Almost all competencies can be developed. And in corporate training, improving the competencies that imply professional knowledge and skills is the most effective and relatively easy, for example: Delegation, performance control, task adjustment, motivation, negotiation, service-related skills, ability, professional knowledge.

These competencies typically include: Responsibility, flexibility, decision making, command, systematic thinking, results orientation, and creativity.

Competencies such as responsibility or a person's result or process orientation are largely unaffected. Making a person ready to take on a certain responsibility and being able to bear it is a difficult task and depends on the development of the person as a whole, even on his self-esteem and aspirations, personal maturity and integrity. Or, for example, decision-making in management activities (although it is often called a function) is a complex combination of a number of personal components based on the willingness to take responsibility. In addition, it is persistence and the ability to analyze the situation, conditions, resources and anticipate changes. A decision is a set goal, that is, action, means the ability to fulfill your decision, etc.

Creativity is the ability to create new things, find non-standard, original solutions, go beyond already known template schemes. It is mainly determined by the flexibility of thinking and the ability to see, analyze, and act in conditions of ambiguity and uncertainty. And influencing the flexibility of thinking in an adult and a mature person is perhaps an insurmountable task for business. For this competence, a person has a constant need for creative activity and his own opinion about it.

Another example is command - in this case indicates a tendency to work in a team. Teamwork skills can be taught. Our company implements projects where we train the team to work together, solve a common problem and negotiate. The effectiveness of such training largely depends on how the team is initially filled with employees who are inclined to work in a team. In this competence, the characteristics of motivation, character, level of conflict, adaptability, the need to be a part of something, the ability to see and feel the nearby colleague, etc., play an important role.

Communication skills are the ability to communicate with people, communicate effectively, establish and maintain relationships, and listen. This skill is developing, but it requires a lot of careful work. Here it is necessary to distinguish competence such as communicative ability and sociability. If the skill can be developed, then sociability, which we mean by the amount of communication a person needs and feels comfortable with, cannot be developed in any way. There are people who have excellent communication skills, but their range of communication and the amount of communication is very limited. They simply cannot handle much interaction.

It is necessary to emphasize such a common competence as leadership, understood as the ability to influence people, motivate them to strive for a goal,

leadership, persuasiveness. Leadership also includes poorly developed components such as readiness to take responsibility, analysis of the situation, ability to foresee its consequences, assessment of available resources, conditions, etc. Of course, there are very common ways to develop decision-making, leadership, creativity, and communication skills. They can be learned. But the development of these abilities depends on the motivation of a person, his natural inclination. It requires deep inner work on yourself.

Often, a person is engaged in the independent development of the above-mentioned powers. Selection of training forms and programs (coaching, mentoring, psychotherapy, counseling, etc.), leading life goals and aspirations. And with due determination, positive results will be achieved.

It is known that the number of key competencies varies from 3 to 140 for different authors. An approximate list of them was presented at the Symposium "Core Competences for Europe" held in Bern in 1996. This includes:

- 1) political and social powers;
- 2) intercultural competences that allow living harmoniously with representatives of other cultures and religions;
- 3) competencies related to oral and written communication; information competence;
- 4) competences that determine the ability to learn throughout life.

In the same year, Jacques Delors, in his lecture "Education: a hidden treasure", identified four global competencies: "learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together, learning to live".

Basic competences are also emphasized by local teachers, for example, A.V. Khutorskoi notes seven groups of basic competences: value-semantic, general cultural, educational and cognitive, informational, communicative, social and labor, personal self. improvement. In addition, each group includes elements of independent learning activities. G.K. Selevko classifies competences by types of activities, fields of science, components of the psychological field, as well as by regions, in the field of public life, production, skills, and across the stages of social maturity and status.

Competence is an integral quality of a person - a competence that is successfully implemented in an activity. In our opinion, the components of competence / competence in any sphere of life can be expressed as follows: cognitive component (knowledge); motivational component; axiological component

(orientation, value relations of the person); practical component (skills, skills, experience); abilities;

Emotional-volitional component (self-control). In this case, competence acts as a competence potential that can be realized in a specific field of activity, it should be effective with the help of self-organization, self-management mechanisms.

Conclusion

In short, there are still no definitive solutions to the problem of developing students' communicative competence. Therefore, it would be no mistake to say that the study of this problem and the conclusion of solutions will bring about innovations in the development of science.

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